

Universität
Basel

Medizinische Fakultät
Departement Public Health

La Source.
Institut et Haute
Ecole de la Santé

Scuola universitaria professionale
della Svizzera italiana

SUPSI

Current quality improvement practices in residential long-term care: a protocol for a mixed methods study

NATIONAL IMPLEMENTATION PROGRAMME – STRENGTHENING
QUALITY OF CARE IN PARTNERSHIP WITH RESIDENTIAL LONG-
TERM CARE FACILITIES FOR OLDER PEOPLE 2022-2026

NIP-Q-UPGRADE

Version 1, 08.01.2024

Author(s): Angelika Rüttimann, Lisa Kästner, Nereide Curreri, Emmanuelle Poncin, Laurie Corna,
Franziska Zúñiga, Bastiaan Van Grootven, on behalf of the NIP-Q-UPGRADE consortium

Institute of Nursing Science (INS), Department of Public Health, University of Basel, Basel
Institut et Haute École de la Santé (La Source), University of Applied Sciences Western Switzerland,
Lausanne
Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana (SUPSI), Manno

National Implementation Programme – **Strengthening quality of care in partnership with
residential long term care facilities for older people 2022–2026 (NIP-Q-UPGRADE)**,
commissioned by the Federal Quality Commission (FQC) to ARTISET with the industry association
CURAVIVA and senesuisse – [Laufende Programme und Projekte \(admin.ch\)](https://www.admin.ch)

The NIP-Q-UPGRADE supports long-term care facilities in data-driven quality improvement based on the national quality indicators.

The National Programme is implemented using implementation science approaches. ARTISET and senesuisse have delegated the scientific management of the programme to their collaboration partner, the University of Basel, Institut for Nursing Science (INS). For its part, the INS works collaboratively with the Institut et Haute École La Source in Lausanne (La Source) and the Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana (SUPSI) to implement the programme nationally and has delegated different sub-aims to the partner institutions. The research institutes' interpretation of the scientifically substantiated results, their conclusions and recommendations to the trustee and to the Federal Quality Commission EQC may differ from the trustee's point of view.

Suggested citation: Angelika Rüttimann, Nereide Curreri, Emmanuelle Poncin, Laurie Corna, Franziska Zúñiga, Bastiaan Van Grootven, on behalf of the NIP-Q-UPGRADE consortium: Current quality improvement practices in residential long-term care: a protocol for a mixed methods study. Mandate on behalf of the National Implementation Programme – Strengthening quality of care in partnership with residential long-term care facilities for older people 2022-2026 (NIP-Q-UPGRADE), Laufende Programme und Projekte ([admin.ch](https://www.admin.ch)). doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10469515.

Table of Contents

Introduction	4
Aim and Objectives	4
Methodology	5
<i>Design</i>	5
<i>Inclusion Criteria</i>	5
Online survey (quantitative part)	5
Interviews with facility leaders (qualitative part a)	6
Workshops with residents and relatives (qualitative part b)	6
<i>Recruitment</i>	7
Online survey (quantitative part)	7
Interviews with facility leaders (qualitative part a)	7
Workshops with residents and relatives (qualitative part b)	8
<i>Variables and Measurements</i>	8
Online survey (quantitative aim 1a)	8
Interviews with facility leaders (qualitative aim 1b)	10
Workshops with residents and relatives (qualitative aim 2)	10
<i>Data collection</i>	10
Online survey (quantitative aim 1a)	11
Interviews with facility leaders (qualitative aim 1b)	11
Workshops with residents and relatives (qualitative aim 2)	11
<i>Data management</i>	11
Online survey (quantitative aim 1a)	11
Interviews and workshops (qualitative aim 1b and aim 2)	12
Data access, security, and storage	12
<i>Data analysis</i>	12
Online survey (quantitative aim 1a)	12
Interviews with facility leaders (qualitative aim 1a)	12
Mixed method analysis of the survey and the facility leader interviews (qualitative aim 1b)	13
Workshops with residents and relatives (qualitative aim 2)	13
Ethical considerations	13
References	14

Introduction

The quality of care provided in long-term care (LTC) facilities is a critical concern in the field of healthcare, especially as the population of older persons continues to grow, and the disability and complexity of health problems amongst LTC facility residents will increase (1-3). Despite the increasing importance placed on quality improvement in LTC facilities (4), there is a need for a comprehensive understanding and analysis of existing practices when organizing care quality improvement, that can contribute to the implementation of a quality improvement program in LTC facilities.

This study is embedded within the NIP-Q-UPGRADE programme, that aims to strengthen LTC facilities in their work with the national quality indicators. An important step is to understand how facilities organise quality improvement and how national quality indicators are integrated in it. The information from this study will be used to develop a national programme in Switzerland to support LTC facilities with organizing quality improvement in the care for their residents.

Aim and Objectives

The overall aim of this study is to identify the current care quality improvement practices in residential Swiss LTC facilities. First, a national survey is conducted (quantitative part). Following this, interviews are held with LTC facility personnel (qualitative part). This information will be combined in a mixed methods study. Lastly, workshops are conducted with residents and relatives (qualitative study 2). There are two major objectives:

1) To provide a comprehensive understanding of how quality improvement for the national quality indicators (pain, malnutrition, polypharmacy, physical restraints use) is organised in Swiss residential long-term care facilities, by first exploring structures and processes of quality improvement in a survey, followed by a more in-depth exploration of its organisation using semi-structured interviews (quan-QUAL mixed methods study). The sub-aims are to:

- a. Identify current structures, practices, and processes for care quality improvement overall, and specifically regarding the current national quality indicators, including the use of data as a basis for care quality improvement (quantitative).
- b. To understand experiences and perceptions with (data-driven) quality improvement for the national medical QIs, and explore barriers and facilitators for (data-driven) care quality improvement (qualitative)

- c. To identify implementation needs for data-driven quality improvement in Swiss residential LTC facilities by combining insights into current practices with experiences in quality improvement of facilities
- 2) Identification of residents and relatives' involvement in quality of care in Swiss LTC facilities through workshops (qualitative). The sub-aim is to:
 - a) Identify residents and relatives' experiences, perceptions, and expectations regarding care quality improvement (e.g., whether and how they have been involved in quality of care improvement and how they would like to be involved), and their perception on successful care quality improvement.

Methodology

Design

An explanatory sequential mixed-methods design (5) is used. Quantitative data will be collected via a survey of LTC facility leaders (aim 1a). The results from the quantitative study serve as a basis to conduct interviews with LTC facility leaders involved in care quality improvement (aim 1b). The qualitative data is collected as a way to further interpret and clarify the results from the quantitative data (5). Then, in a mixed method study, both the quantitative and qualitative data will be connected and summarized to inform how to support LTC facilities in care quality improvement (aim 1c). Additional qualitative data will be collected via resident and relative workshops (aim 2). The results from this additional qualitative study (aim 2) helps to get an even broader understanding of current care quality improvement practices in Swiss LTC facilities.

Inclusion Criteria

Online survey (quantitative part)

The online survey is conducted among leaders in Swiss LTC facilities. The inclusion criteria for facilities to participate in the survey is to be a Swiss LTC facility that bills services according to the national health service law (KVG). As a result, all LTC facilities in Switzerland – approximately 1'530 facilities – will be invited to participate in the survey (7). Only one survey per facility will be allowed to be submitted. A survey can be filled in by multiple LTC facility leaders. In case of multi-sited facilities or group of facilities, each individual site or campus can complete the survey. The survey targets LTC facility leaders who are facility managers, quality of care coordinators, nurse experts or other professionals closely involved in care quality improvement processes and can speak German, French or Italian.

Interviews with facility leaders (qualitative part a)

In this qualitative phase we aim to include around 12-15 LTC facilities from the three different language regions. LTC facilities will be included if they have participated and provided complete data in the online survey. We aim to select a mixed sample of facility leaders which allows to gather a diverse perspective of care quality improvement structures and practices (e.g., identify contextual differences, inner context challenges, process differences), and to identify needs for improvement. To achieve this, a recruitment matrix will be drafted where we want to balance diversity on the following components 1) language region in Switzerland (n = 9 German; n = 3 French; n = 3 Italian), 2) canton, 3) type of LTC facility (public; private), 4) type of participant (balance of managers, quality coordinators, nurse experts), 5) quality of care coordinator in LTC facility (no; yes), 6) reported data-driven quality improvement initiatives (no; yes), 7) use of PDCA cycle to improve quality of care (no; yes), and 8) current quality improvement project (no; yes; If yes= which indicators?). The final sample size will depend on insights emerging during the interview process which indicate the need for more information or indicate that data saturation has been achieved. We anticipate that 20 interviews will be the maximum. In each facility an interview with 1-3 leaders involved in care quality improvement processes is planned (total 12-45 participants assuming a sample of around 15 facilities; up to 60 participants maximum).

Workshops with residents and relatives (qualitative part b)

For workshops with residents and their relatives, four LTC facility who are willing to conduct workshops in their facility will be included (three in the German speaking region, one in the French speaking region). We aim to include three to five relatives and three to five residents per LTC facility. Residents will be included if they are able to speak and understand German or French, have a non-critical health status, a Cognitive Performance Scale score ≤ 3 (retrieved from routine data), and who have given an informed consent. Residents with severe cognitive impairment, in end-of-life situation, who are unwell at the day of the scheduled interview or with psychiatric problems that impede an interview will be excluded due to their inability to physically and mentally participate in a 90-minute workshop. Relatives will be included if they are able to speak and understand German or French, visiting regularly (minimum once/month) and if they are involved in medical decisions regarding the resident. Relatives of people with severe cognitive impairment will be approached to be included in the workshops to represent those residents that cannot speak for themselves and to make the most representative sample possible. The above resident and relative information are not retrieved or recorded by the research team, but by the facility staff who will assess eligibility of the resident and relatives.

The staff will only communicate eligibility to the research team, but no resident or relative information.

Recruitment

Online survey (quantitative part)

Recruitment takes place for two months, starting in August 2023. The survey will be online until October 2023, with the aim to have a response rate of 10%. Based on this response rate, the team will decide to extend the duration of the survey. The survey recruitment method consists of two sequential recruitment sets. First, an online newsletter, including a study information sheet, is sent by the two national provider organizations of LTC facilities, CURAVIVA, which targets public facilities and senesuisse, which targets private facilities. This newsletter includes a description of the study and a link to the survey. Also, senesuisse distributes the survey link via a personal letter to all LTC facilities, and CURAVIVA distributes the survey link via a personal letter to their collective members. A second recruitment set is used and adapted regularly according to the response rate and recruitment success and will include reminders via cantonal LTC associations, promotion of the survey on conferences, using social media, webpage flyers, email, and information sessions. Participants will be recruited until the sample size of 10% of all Swiss facilities is reached. Participants can give their informed consent electronically in the online survey for their participation.

Interviews with facility leaders (qualitative part a)

LTC facility leaders that fit the inclusion criteria will be purposively recruited until the sample size (see inclusion criteria) is reached by using the contact details provided voluntarily in the online survey via email and/ or telephone. To be able to recruit LTC facility leaders, there will be an additional informed consent at the end of the survey to de-anonymize leaders contact details and the following survey items: 1) language region, 2) canton, 3) type of LTC facility, 4) type of participant, 5) if they have a quality-of-care coordinator, 6) reported data-driven quality improvement initiatives, 7) use of PDCA cycle to improve quality of care, and 8) current quality improvement project. If participants consent, their survey data can be linked to the interview using a pseudo-anonymous code. We will recruit a heterogeneous sample of LTC facility leaders until our sample size reached. Data from survey participants who do not want to participate in the interview will be completely anonymous. The recruitment email for the interviews includes a description of the study. Recruitment for interviews takes place between October and January 2023. Prior to the interviews, participants will receive an informed consent form, which will be discussed before the interview.

Workshops with residents and relatives (qualitative part b)

We aim to recruit in total four LTC facilities, at least one facility in the total four regional conferences of the Conference of Health Directors¹ based on their willingness to participate in workshops and based on how the facility involves residents and relatives in quality improvement. They will be asked during interview in the previous step (qualitative part a) if they would be willing to conduct resident and relative workshops at their facility. Facilities will be selected based on their willingness to participate in the interviews and based on their involvement of residents in quality improvement. A study ID number will be documented for these four consenting facilities, which will be linked with the study ID of the survey and interviews in the previous step. This study ID number will be stored on separate server files. Residents and relatives who meet the inclusions criteria will be contacted by the facility manager, either in their room (residents) or while on site, via telephone and/or email (relatives). Facility managers provide information about the study and ask for their willingness to participate in the workshops. Resident and relative recruitment is primarily coordinated by the facility manager after clear instructions by the research team (e.g., facility managers receive recruitment instructions, information letter and informed consent for participants, and instructions for an information session if necessary).

Variables and Measurements

In the following section, variables and measurements for both quantitative (survey) and qualitative data (LTC leader interview and resident and relative workshops) will be described.

Online survey (quantitative aim 1a)

The questions of the survey will be based on a non-exhaustive search for surveys on quality of care improvement in LTC facilities on Pubmed and Embase (restricted to 10 years), conducted by one researcher, as well as on the results of the SHURP 2018 study (8) which has already collected data on the four national quality indicator themes and on care quality improvement processes. The Quality Assurance & Performance Improvement framework (QAPI) from the Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services (CMS) in the USA serves as guiding framework for the question on quality improvement (9, 10). QAPI consists of the following five elements:

¹ The four regional conferences are: Conférence latine des affaires sanitaires et sociales (CLASS) cantons BE, FR, GE, JU, NE, TI, VD, VS / Northwest Switzerland Health Directors' Conference (NWGDK) cantons AG, BE, BL, BS, JU, SO / Health Directors' Conference of the Cantons of Eastern Switzerland and FL (GDK-Ost) Cantons AI, AR, GL, GR, SG, SH, TG, ZH, FL / Central Switzerland Health Directors' Conference (ZGDK) Cantons LU, NW, OW, SZ, UR, ZG.

1. **Design and Scope** (e.g., quality program addresses quality holistically including clinical and management practices, quality of life and resident choices)
2. **Governance and Leadership** (e.g., residents are surveyed, appropriate resources are in place, responsible person for quality efforts exists, policies have been developed, safety culture is fostered)
3. **Feedback, Data Systems and Monitoring** (e.g., quality is monitored and data from multiple sources are collected, feedback systems are working, national medical QIs and benchmarking are used, goals have been set, adverse event are monitored)
4. **Performance Improvement Projects** (e.g., concentrated efforts on a particular problem are implemented)
5. **Systematic Analysis and Systemic Action** (e.g., use of a thorough, comprehensive and structured approach to identify problems, their causes, and the implications for change, use of the Root Cause Analysis method)

Thus, survey questions can be about existing practices, structures, and processes in the LTC facility regarding care quality improvement with focus on the four national quality indicator themes (pain, weight loss, polypharmacy, physical restraint use) and three potential new quality indicator measurement themes (pressure ulcers, advance care planning and medication reviews), e.g., if the facility monitors performance based on QIs; Which methods are used for care quality improvement; How residents, relatives and staff are involved in care quality improvement. The survey questions will also focus on existing data-driven care quality improvement practices (e.g., If they use benchmarks to improve quality of care) or challenges and opportunities for current care quality improvement practices.

This preliminary information will be used to generate question domains via a brainstorming exercise within the research team and then further specified to questions using a team discussion and feedback round within the consortium of the NIP-Q-UPGRADE programme. The study team will then use an internal rating regarding the item's relevance, where the highest scored items will be used in the final survey version that aims to have around 30 questions (11). The survey will then be translated into German, French and Italian. For cognitive testing, three nurse experts or persons from LTC facility management with experience in residential LTC and two nurse researchers from the INS, La Source or SUPSI are asked to give feedback on the questions to indicate how they interpret the question (at least one person who speaks German, French or Italian as a first language). After adapting the survey and creating the technical version of the survey with LimeSurvey in the three

different languages, a pilot test is conducted by sending the pilot survey to three nurse experts or persons from LTC facility management with experience in residential LTC and two nurse researchers from the INS, LA Source or SUPSI. They will receive an electronic feedback sheet regarding the items' comprehensibility and readability and an overall rating of the instruction clarity of the surveys, and user-friendliness of the surveys' design (including its length). Written feedback will be discussed during a group discussion with the pilot participants. A final survey is created after receiving feedback from the pilot survey and solving logistical and technical issues.

Additional Survey Variables

The following additional variables will be included in the survey: individual characteristics (e.g., position in institution and tasks involvement regarding care quality improvement); facility characteristics (e.g., ownership type, number of beds); the roles of the persons who are responsible of implementation for care quality improvement programs; and whether the participant would be willing to voluntarily participate in an interview that follows the survey.

Interviews with facility leaders (qualitative aim 1b)

The semi-structured interviews will include questions with a focus on how care quality improvement is organized in the LTC facility, leaders' perception regarding data-driven care quality improvement strategies (e.g., if they work with benchmarks), what factors hinder and facilitate the successful organization of care quality improvement in general, specifically regarding the themes of the national medical QIs, and what support they need to organize care quality improvement. With permission of the participants, survey responses will be reviewed before the interview. Additional interview questions will focus on clarifying or deepening survey response options. Lastly, they will be asked if they are willing to hold workshops with residents and relatives in their facility (qualitative aim 2).

Workshops with residents and relatives (qualitative aim 2)

The workshops with residents and relatives include topics and questions about their experiences and expectations regarding how care is provided to them (in the themes pertaining to the national medical QIs specifically), ideas and perceptions regarding how to improve care, and how they are involved and wish to be involved in care. This includes their perceptions on what constitutes good quality of care and what can be considered successful quality improvement. The workshops can help to complete the information on the current quality of care provided in Swiss LTC facilities and can contribute valuable information on what further steps are necessary in care quality improvement practices and structures.

Data collection

In the following section, data collection for both quantitative (survey) and qualitative data (LTC leader interview and resident and relative workshops) will be described.

Online survey (quantitative aim 1a)

The survey takes place via the online survey instrument LimeSurvey. The survey will be online until end of October 2023 with a possibility for extension depending on response rate. Since data collection and recruitment for the online survey take place within the same steps, the data collection and methods to increase response rate are described in the section "Recruitment".

Interviews with facility leaders (qualitative aim 1b)

One individual or group interview will take place per participating facility. Interviews will be conducted on-site or online by the research teams from INS, La Source or SUPSI, depending on the language region of the LTC facility. An interview guide will be developed by the research team. The semi-structured interviews will include open questions to stimulate the conversation and specific questions to gather in-depth information (see variables and measurements). The interviews will be moderated by one researcher. Interviews with facility leaders will be audio recorded and transcribed. No direct personal identifiers will be transcribed, and data will only be linked to a pseudonymised study ID number.

Workshops with residents and relatives (qualitative aim 2)

Resident and relative workshops will take place at the participating facility and will be led by the research team. A semi-structured interview guide for the workshops will be drafted, with open questions to stimulate the conversation and specific questions to gather in-depth information. During the workshops, a knowledge map is used for verbal answers, which can also stimulate the discussion. The workshops will be moderated by one researcher and a second researcher will be present for observing and taking notes. Workshops will be audio recorded and transcribed. A study ID number will be documented for these four consenting facilities, which will be linked with the study ID of the survey and interviews in the previous step. This study ID number will also be stored on a separate server file, for more information see section "Data management".

Data management

This section contains information on the data management plan.

Online survey (quantitative aim 1a)

Data will be collected from LTC facility leaders via an online survey (using LimeSurvey) and processed using R studio. Data will be exported from LimeSurvey in a .csv file and saved on a password protected server file of the University of Basel. The original data will be kept in a separate folder that cannot be modified once stored on the secured INS server. Participants

in the national survey will receive an anonymous survey number. Survey participants who consent to participate in the follow-up interviews will receive a study ID number, which will be linked to the survey number and the name of the facility. This code list will be stored in a password protected server file separate from the study data. The coding list of LTC facility name and contact details will be saved on a separate server file only accessible to the principal investigator and researcher coordinating the study.

Interviews and workshops (qualitative aim 1b and aim 2)

The data of the interviews with facility leaders and workshops with residents and relatives will be digitally recorded and transcribed. Facilities who participated in the interview and who consent to participate in the resident workshop will receive an additional study ID number, which will be linked to the study ID number from the interview, the survey number and the name of the facility. This code list will be stored in a password protected server file separate from the study data. No personal information from interviews and workshops will be documented or analysed. Audio recordings and transcripts will be saved on a password protected server file of the University of Basel and will only be identified through their study ID number. After the study has been completed, audio recordings will be deleted.

Data access, security, and storage

Data will be saved and stored on the secured research server of the INS, which ensures regular backups and has adequate protection. Access to the server will be restricted to team members and through password protected connections. All Data (survey data, recorded interviews and internal documents from LTC facilities (regarding quality improvement)) will be kept on the secured INS server and deleted after the study has been completed and published. Data will be archived for a minimum of ten years. After the project, the principal investigator of the institution will be responsible for archiving the data.

Data analysis

Online survey (quantitative aim 1a)

The data is analyzed with descriptive statistics (e.g., percentage, median, IQR) using R studio. The percentage of missing will be assessed for the quantitative data. Open questions will be analyzed using thematic analysis (12).

Interviews with facility leaders (qualitative aim 1a)

An iterative method of reflexive thematic analysis according to Braun & Clarke (13) will be used to analyze the data from LTC facility leader interviews, where knowledge can be gained to understand participants' experiences and needs regarding care quality improvement practices, processes and structures within their LTC facility. The QAPI framework (9, 10) can

guide the reflection on themes to describe best practice examples based on various dimensions of care quality improvement practices. The Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR) by Damschroder et al. (14) can guide the reflection on themes that hinder and facilitate care quality improvement in LTC facilities. Qualitative data is analyzed using MAXQDA (15).

Mixed method analysis of the survey and the facility leader interviews (qualitative aim 1b)

Using an explanatory sequential design, there will be three stages of analysis in this study: 1) analysis of the quantitative data 2) analysis of the qualitative data, and 3) an analysis of both types of data together. This integration of the data extends the initial quantitative findings using the qualitative findings and merges them together in the analysis (16). The integration happens during the analysis of the data, at the interpretation-level, where both types of data are connected and summarized using a joint display (6). Discrepancies and areas of convergence between the qualitative and quantitative data are discussed within the research team to develop an overall understanding of the data. The final joint display of results from the online survey and the interviews with facility leaders allow for new insights beyond the insights from each type of data separately (17). The results will be discussed with a sounding board of six to ten LTC facility leaders to jointly determine the need for action to improve and maintain quality of care regarding the national quality indicators and care quality improvement in general. These facility leaders are part of an established regional sounding board within the NIP-Q-UPGRADE programma.

Workshops with residents and relatives (qualitative aim 2)

A social constructivist approach to qualitative research is adopted and the iterative method of reflexive thematic analysis according to Braun & Clarke (13) will be used to analyze the data from resident and relative workshops. Knowledge maps and personal notes from the researcher will also be used to inductively generate themes regarding resident and relatives' experiences, perception and expectations regarding quality of care, and their perception on successful quality improvement. Qualitative data is analyzed using MAXQDA (15). The findings of the workshops will also be discussed with the same sounding board mentioned above of six to ten LTC facility leaders to jointly determine the need for action to improve and maintain quality of care.

Ethical considerations

An electronic informed consent will be obtained from survey participants via the online survey and an electronic or paper informed consent will be obtained from interview participants prior

to the interviews and workshops. The form includes information about the study, participation modalities, participants' rights, potential risks, and benefits, data use and confidentiality, and a declaration of consent to participate. Confidentiality of the results is guaranteed for all facilities and study participants.

Since we use the data collected in the online survey as a basis to select best practice examples, we need to be able to contact some of the participating LTC facilities to ask them about their interest to participate in further qualitative investigations. Since we ask to voluntarily provide contact details and the name of the institution, some survey surveys might not be anonymous at the individual or at the facility level, but the data will stay confidential and will be de-identified for all data analysis. The name of the LTC facility will be coded. The coding list will be saved on a separate server file only accessible to the principle investigator and researcher coordinating the study.

A summary of the protocol was submitted to the seven responsible ethics committees in Switzerland (Ethics Committee of northwest/central Switzerland, Ethics commission Ticino, Commission Cantonale d'Ethique de la Recherche sur l'ötre humain (CCER), Commission cantonale d'ethique de la recherche sur l'etre humain CER-VD, Kantonale Ethikkommission Bern, Ethikkommission Ostschweiz, and Ethikkommission Zürich) for clarification of responsibility. According to the clarification of responsibility of June 2023, this study does not fall under the scope of the Human Research Act (Req-2023-00775).

References

1. Barker RO, Hanratty B, Kingston A, Ramsay SE, Matthews FE. Changes in health and functioning of care home residents over two decades: what can we learn from population-based studies? *Age and Ageing*. 2020;50(3):921-7.
2. Elderly population [Internet]. 2014. Available from: <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/content/data/8d805ea1-en>.
3. OECD (2019), *Health at a Glance 2019: OECD Indicators*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/4dd50c09-en>.
4. OECD/European Union (2013), *A Good Life in Old Age?: Monitoring and Improving Quality in Long-term Care*, OECD Health Policy Studies, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264194564-en>.
5. Edmonds WA, Kennedy TD. *An Applied Guide to Research Designs: Quantitative, Qualitative, and Mixed Methods* Thousand Oaks, California. 2017. Available from: <https://methods.sagepub.com/book/an-applied-guide-to-research-designs-2e>.

6. Fetzters MD, Curry LA, Creswell JW. Achieving Integration in Mixed Methods Designs—Principles and Practices. *Health Services Research*. 2013;48(6pt2):2134-56.
7. Federal Statistical Office. Etablissements médico-sociaux 2021 [Available from: <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/fr/home/statistiques/sante/systeme-sante/etablissements-medico-sociaux.html>].
8. Zúñiga F, Favez L, Baumann S, Kindlimann A, Oeri A, Benkert B, et al. SHURP 2018—Schlussbericht. Personal und Pflegequalität in Pflegeinstitutionen in der Deutschschweiz und Romandie. Universität Basel. 2021.
9. Bakerjian D, Zisberg A. Applying the advancing excellence in America's nursing homes circle of success to improving and sustaining quality. *Geriatric Nursing*. 2013;34(5):402-11.
10. Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services. QAPI at a Glance: A Step by Step Guide to Implementing Quality Assurance and Performance Improvement (QAPI) in Your Nursing Home. 2012.
11. Kost RG, Correa da Rosa J. Impact of survey length and compensation on validity, reliability, and sample characteristics for Ultrashort-, Short-, and Long-Research Participant Perception Surveys. *Journal of Clinical and Translational Science*. 2018;2(1):31-7.
12. Braun V, Clarke V. Conceptual and design thinking for thematic analysis. *Qualitative Psychology*. 2022;9(1):3.
13. Braun V, Clarke V, Hayfield N, Gareth T. Thematic analysis. In: Liamputtong P, editor. *Handbook of research methods in health social sciences*. Singapore: Springer Nature; 2019. p. 843-60.
14. Damschroder LJ, Reardon CM, Widerquist MAO, Lowery J. The updated Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research based on user feedback. *Implementation Science*. 2022;17(1):1-16.
15. VERBI Software. MAXQDA 2020 [computer software]. Berlin, Germany: VERBI Software.2019.
16. Creswell JW, and Vicki L. Plano Clark. . *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. 2nd ed ed: SAGE Publications; 2011.
17. Teddlie C, and Abbas Tashakkori. *Foundations of Mixed Methods Research: Integrating Quantitative and Qualitative Techniques in the Social and Behavioral Sciences*: Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications; 2008.